

**A REVIEW ON FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF
TRANSDERMAL PATCHES FOR PEPTIC ULCER****Pooja H. V.***, **Arpitha B. M.²**, **Manyashree S.²**, **Mohith H.²**, **Pooja V.²**, **Chandana K. P.²**^{1,2}Department of Pharmaceutics, Ikon Pharmacy College, Bheemanahalli, Bidadi, Bangaluru,
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ABSTRACT

Peptic ulcer disease is a common gastrointestinal disorder characterized by open sores or lesions in the lining of the stomach or upper part of the small intestine. It is primarily caused by *Helicobacter pylori* infection, excessive use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), stress or lifestyle factors. Symptoms typically include burning stomach pain, bloating, nausea and in severe cases, gastrointestinal bleeding. Conventional treatment involves oral administration of anti-ulcer medications, which may be associated with poor patient compliance, gastrointestinal side effects and variable drug bioavailability. Transdermal drug delivery offers a promising alternative for the treatment of peptic ulcers by allowing steady and controlled drug release through the skin, bypassing the gastrointestinal tract. This method enhances bioavailability, reduces dosing frequency and minimizes

systemic side effects. The formulation of transdermal patches involves selecting appropriate polymers and plasticizers to ensure drug stability, skin adhesion and consistent release rates. The development of transdermal patches for peptic ulcer therapy represents an innovative and patient-friendly approach. By improving drug delivery and reducing complications associated with oral medications, this system has the potential to enhance therapeutic outcomes and overall patient compliance in the management of peptic ulcer disease.

KEYWORDS: PUD, NSAID's, Transdermal Patches.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Peptic ulcer

Peptic ulcer disease is a problem of the gastrointestinal tract characterized by mucosal damage secondary to pepsin and gastric acid secretion. It usually occurs in the stomach and proximal duodenum, it occurs in the lower esophagus, the distal duodenum or the jejunum as in unopposed hypersecretory states such as Zollinger-Ellison syndrome.^[1] The word ‘peptic’ refers to pepsin a stomach enzyme that break down proteins. Peptic ulcer located in stomach is called gastric ulcer.^[2]

Fig. 1: Peptic Ulcer.

ETIOLOGY

Peptic ulcers, despite being a common gastrointestinal disorder, have a complex and multifactorial etiology. Understanding the various factors contributing to ulcer formation is crucial for effective management and prevention. The primary causes of peptic ulcers include *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection, the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory (NSAIDs) and less commonly stress-related mucosal damage.^[3]

- **NSAIDs:** NSAIDs are commonly used for their analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antipyretic properties. However, their use is associated with an increased risk of peptic ulcer perforation (PPU). Approximately 25% of chronic NSAID users will develop peptic ulcer disease (PUD), and 2%-4% may experience bleeding or perforation.
- **H. Pylori:** Recurrent peptic ulcer disease (PUD) predominantly occurs in patients with *H. pylori* infection, suggesting that *H. pylori* play a significant role in the development of

PUD and its complications. While proton pump inhibitor therapy significantly reduces the risk of recurrent *H. pylori* infection, its efficacy in reducing ulcers is modest in NSAID users.

- **Smoking:** Tobacco is thought to inhibit pancreatic bicarbonate secretion, leading to increased acidity duodenum. It also inhibits the healing of duodenal ulcers. However, in some studies, there was no difference in tobacco use between patients with non-*H. pylori*, non-NSAID duodenal ulcers and those with *H. pylori* related ulcers, indicating a limited role of smoking. This indicated that smoking did not increase the risk of ulcer recurrence once the *H. pylori* had been eradicated.^[4]

EPIDEMIOLOGY

PUD continues to cause significant morbidity and mortality worldwide, with more than half of the world population infected. It is thought to be responsible for high health care costs of greater than 3 billion annually. In the United States, PUD affects 4.6 million people annually. The lifetime prevalence of PUD is estimated as high as 10% and is less prevalent in developed countries. PUD is the most common cause of upper gastrointestinal bleeding in the Western world; a systematic review estimated the annual incidence of hemorrhage at approximately 19 to 57 cases per 100,000 individuals. Other sequelae of PUD include abdominal pain, gastric outlet obstruction and ulcer perforation. Together these complications result in approximately 150,000 hospitalizations annually in the United States.^[5]

SYMPTOMS

Most common symptom of peptic ulcer is abdominal discomfort. This discomfort comes and goes for several days of week, generally occurs 2 to 3 hrs after a meal, in the middle of night, when stomach is empty. Other symptoms include;

- Blood loss leading to anemia
- Weight loss
- Poor appetite
- Bloating
- Nausea and vomiting
- Stomach pain and burning
- Blood in vomit

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Mechanisms of mucosal injury in peptic ulcers: Peptic ulcers result from an imbalance between aggressive factors, such as gastric acid, pepsin and reactive oxygen species (ROS) and protective mechanisms within the gastric and duodenal mucosa. Several key mechanisms contribute to mucosal injury in peptic ulcers:

1. **Helicobacter pylori Infection:** *H. pylori* colonization of the gastric mucosa leads to chronic inflammation, which disrupts the mucosal barrier and impairs its protective function. The bacterium's virulence factors, including cytotoxin-associated gene A (CagA) and vacuolating cytotoxin A (VacA), contribute to mucosal injury by inducing epithelial cell damage and inflammation.
2. **NSAID-Induced Damage:** Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) inhibit cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes, resulting in decreased prostaglandin synthesis. Prostaglandins play a crucial role in maintaining mucosal integrity by promoting mucus and bicarbonate secretion, enhancing mucosal blood flow and stimulating epithelial cell proliferation. NSAID-induced COX inhibition reduces these protective mechanisms, rendering the mucosa susceptible to injury from gastric acid and pepsin.
3. **Gastric Acid and Pepsin:** Gastric acid and pepsin contribute to mucosal injury by directly damaging epithelial cells and disrupting the mucosal barrier. Acid secretion is regulated by the proton pump (H⁺/K⁺-ATPase) located on parietal cells, while pepsinogen is secreted by chief cells and activated to pepsin in an acidic environment. Excessive acid secretion or impaired mucosal defense mechanisms can lead to acid-peptic damage and ulcer formation.

TYPES OF PEPTIC ULCER

1. On the basis of location, Peptic ulcers are categorized as follows;
 - **Gastric Ulcer:** Occurrence of ulcer in the stomach, more commonly in older agegroup.
 - **Duodenal Ulcer:** Occurrence of ulcer in the duodenum. They occur commonly in younger individuals and are evenly distributed among various socioeconomic groups. These patients have higher than normal levels of acid secretion rates.
2. Depending on severity, peptic ulcers are classified as;
 - **Acute Peptic Ulcer:** These ulcers involve tissues to the depth of the submucosa. They may arise in the form of single or multiple lesions. They are found in many sites of stomach and in the first few centimetres of duodenum.

DIAGNOSTIC TEST FOR PEPTIC ULCER

- **Blood test:** Blood tests can be used by physicians to look for symptoms of peptic ulcer complications or an *H. pylori* infection. A medical practitioner will draw blood from you for an NIH blood test and the sample will be sent to a lab.
- **Stool test:** Doctors may use stool tests to detect an *H. pylori* infection. They will provide you with a container to collect a stool sample and give instructions on where to send or deliver it for testing.
- An upper gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopy involves a doctor using a flexible tube with a camera, known as an endoscope, to inspect the lining of your upper GI tract, which includes the esophagus, stomach and duodenum. During the procedure, the doctor may take biopsies by passing a tool through the endoscope to collect small tissue samples from the stomach lining. These samples are then analyzed by a pathologist under a microscope.^[6]

Fig. 2: Upper GI endoscopy.

TREATMENT

The goal of therapy for peptic ulcer disease is to relieve symptoms, heal craters, prevent recurrences and prevent complications. Medical therapy should include treatment with drugs and attempt to accomplish the following

- 1) Reduce gastric acidity by mechanisms that inhibit or neutralize acid secretion
- 2) Coat ulcer craters to prevent acid and pepsin from penetrating to the ulcer base
- 3) Provide a prostaglandin analog
- 4) Remove environmental factors such as NSAIDs and smoking
- 5) Reduce emotional stress (in a subset of patients)

ALLOPATHIC MEDICATION**Table: Allopathic medication for peptic ulcer.**

Category	Medication	Mechanism of action	Adverse effects
Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs)	Omeprazole, Lansoprazole, Rabeprazole, Esomeprazole, Pantoprazole	Inhibition of the gastric H ⁺ /K ⁺ -ATPase (proton pump) enzyme system	Headache Abdominal pain, Diarrhea, Nausea, Vomiting, Constipation, Flatulence, Vitamin B12 deficiency, Osteoporosis
H2 Receptor Blockers	Cimetidine	Blocking the action of histamine at the	Headache, Anxiety, Depression, Dizziness, Cardiovascular
Antacids	Aluminium hydroxide Magnesium hydroxide	Increases gastric pH to Causes osmotic retention of fluid Causes osmotic retention of fluid	Frequency not defined: Nausea Vomiting Hypophosphatemia Chalky Taste Constipation Abdominal Cramping, Diarrhea
Potassium Competitive Acid Blocker	Vonoprazan	Inhibits H ⁺ , K ⁺ -ATPase in gastric parietal cells at the final stage of the acid secretory pathway	Nasopharyngitis Fall Confusion, Diarrhea, Upper respiratory tract inflammation, Eczema, Constipation, Back Pain
Cytoprotective Agent	Misoprostol Sucralfate	Stimulate mucus production and enhance blood flow throughout the lining of the gastrointestinal tract	Abdominal pain Headache Constipation

PREVENTION AND CONTROL

Adopting certain lifestyle habits can help reduce the risk of developing peptic ulcers, such as:

- Avoiding the combination of alcohol and medication
- Limiting alcohol consumption to no more than two drinks per day
- Washing your hands regularly to prevent infections
- Reducing the use of ibuprofen, aspirin and naproxen

Additionally, maintaining a healthy lifestyle by quitting smoking, refraining from tobacco use and eating a balanced diet rich in fruits, vegetables and whole grains can further help to prevent the development of peptic ulcers.^[7]

COMPLICATION

Psychological stress and physical stress affect the development of ulcers because stress aggravates gastroduodenal blood flow, reduces acid buffering in the duodenum and diminishes gastric hypersecretion. Stress tends to be uncontrolled and unpredictable, promotes the onset of disease and is one of the most common risk factors for PUD.

In addition, peptic ulcer disease (PUD) can lead to serious complications if left untreated.

The major complications include

1. Gastrointestinal Bleeding (Most Common)

Due to erosion of blood vessels in the ulcer bed.

2. Perforation (Life-Threatening)

Full-thickness ulceration leads to perforation into the peritoneal cavity.

3. Penetration

Ulcer erodes into adjacent organs (e.g., pancreas, liver).

4. Gastric Outlet Obstruction

Due to chronic inflammation, edema, or scarring in the pyloric region.

5. Malignant Transformation (Rare)

Chronic gastric ulcers may undergo malignant changes, especially if *H. pylori* is present.^[8]

1.2 TRANSDERMAL PATCHES INTRODUCTION

Transdermal patch (Skin patch) uses a special membrane to control the rate at which the liquid drug contained in the reservoir within the patch can pass through the skin and into the bloodstream. Some drugs must be combined with substances, such as alcohol that increase their ability to penetrate the skin in order to be used in a skin patch.^[9] Now a day's several patches are available in market for transdermal use. Some of them are: Clonidine, Testosterone, Fentanyl, Nicotine, Hormones etc. Transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) is a widely as cosmetic, topical and transdermal delivery systems. Transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS) are dosage forms designed to transport drugs into viable epidermal and dermal tissues for localized therapeutic effects, while a significant portion of the drug enters systemic circulation. Transdermal patches offer several advantages over conventional oral or injectable routes, including controlled drug absorption, more consistent plasma

concentrations, improved bioavailability by bypassing first-pass hepatic metabolism and the avoidance of enzymatic or pH-related drug degradation. Additionally, they allow for simple and painless application.^[10]

The main components of transdermal drug delivery system is release liners, adhesive, membrane, drug, backing laminates.^[11]

1.3 TYPES OF TRANSDERMAL PATCHES

Single layer drug in adhesive: In this type the adhesive layer contains the drug. The adhesive layer not only serves to adhere the various layers together and also responsible for the releasing the drug to the skin. The adhesive layer is surrounded by a temporary liner and a backing.

Fig. 3: Single layer patch.

Multi -layer drug in adhesive: This type is also similar to the single layer but it contains an immediate drug-release-layer and other layer will be a controlled release along with the adhesive layer. The adhesive layer is responsible for the releasing of the drug. This patch also has a temporary liner-layer and a permanent backing.

Fig. 4: Multi layer patch.

Reservoir system: In this system the drug reservoir is embedded between an impervious backing layer and a rate controlling membrane. The drug releases only through the rate controlling membrane, which can be micro porous or non porous. In the drug reservoir

compartment, the drug can be in the form of a solution, suspension, gel or dispersed in a solid polymer matrix.^[12]

Fig. 5: Reservoir patch.

Matrix patch: It has a drug layer of a semi-solid matrix containing a drug solution or suspension dispersed within a polymer pad in direct contact with the skin. The adhesive layer in this patch surrounds the drug layer partially overlaying.^[13]

Fig. 6: Matrix patch.

1.4 BASIC COMPONENTS OF TRANSDERMAL PATCH

1. Polymers: Polymers are the important parameter of TDDS, which control the release of the drug from the device. Polymer matrix can be prepared by dispersion of drug in liquid or solid state synthetic polymer base. Companies involved in the field of transdermal delivery concentrate on a few selective polymeric systems.

The polymers utilized for TDDS can be classified as,

Natural Polymers: Cellulose derivatives, zein, gelatin, shellac, waxes, gums.

Synthetic Elastomers: Polybutadiene, hydriin rubber, polyisobutylene, silicon acrylonitrile, neoprene, butylrubber.

Synthetic Polymers: Polyvinyl alcohol, polyvinylchloride, polyethylene, polyacrylate, polyamide, polyurea, polyvinylpyrrolidone etc.

The following criteria should be satisfied for a polymer to be used in transdermal system.

- Molecular weight and chemical functionality of the polymer should be such that specific drug diffuses properly and get released through it.
- The polymer should be stable, non-reactive, easily manufactured and fabricated into the desired product.
- The polymer and its degradation product must be non-toxic to the host.

2. Drug: For successfully developing a TDDS, the drug should be chosen with great care. The following are some of the desirable properties of a drug for transdermal delivery.

Physiochemical properties

- The drug should have a molecular weight less than approximately 1000 Dalton.
- The drug should have affinity for both lipophilic and hydrophilic phases.
- The drug should have low melting point.

Biological properties

- The drug should be potent with a daily dose of the order of a few mg/days.
- The half life should be short.
- The drug must not induce a cutaneous irritant or allergic response.
- Drug which degrades in the GI tract are suitable for transdermal delivery.

3. Permeation enhancers: To increase the permeability of stratum corneum so as to attain higher therapeutic levels of the drug penetration enhancer interact with structural component of stratum corneum i.e. protein and lipids. The enhancement of absorption of oil soluble drugs is apparently due to partial leaching of the epidermal lipids by chemical enhancers, resulting in the improvement of skin condition for wetting and transepithelial and transfollicular penetration.

4. Adhesives: The pressure sensitive adhesive maintains an intimate contact between patch and the skin surface. E.g. polyacrylates, polyisobutylene and silicon based adhesive. The adhesive system should fulfill the following criteria;

- * Should not irritate or sensitize the skin.
- * Should be easily removed.
- * Should not leave an unwashable residue on the skin.

* Should have excellent contact with skin.

5. Backing laminate: The primary function is to provide a good bond to the drug reservoir, prevent drug from leaving the dosage forms through the top. It is impermeable substance that protect the product during use on the skin. E.g. metallic plastic laminate, occlusive base plate (aluminium foil) adhesive foam pad (flexible polyurethane) etc.

6. Release liner: During storage release liner prevents the loss of the drug that has migrated into adhesive layer. It is therefore regarded as a part of primary packaging material. E.g. paper fabric, polyethylene, polyvinylchloride etc.

Other excipients: Solvents such as chloroform, methanol, acetone are used to prepare drug reservoir. In addition plasticizers such as castor oil, propylene glycol etc are added to provide plasticity to the patch.^[14]

Fig. 9: TDDS patch.

1.5 ADVANTAGES OF TDDS

- Hepatic first pass metabolism, salivary metabolism and intestinal metabolism are avoided.
- Ease of usage makes it possible for patients to self-administer these systems.
- Drugs showing gastrointestinal irritation and absorption can be suitably administered through skin.
- Due to reduced frequency of dosing there is better patient compliance.
- Adverse effects are minimized due to a steady and optimum blood concentration time profile.^[15]

1.6 DISADVANTAGES OF TDDS

- Many hydrophilic drugs cannot pass or very slowly permeates the skin. This will affect the therapeutic efficacy of the drug.
- Many problems like itching, edema, erythema etc. may be seen due to patches.
- There may be some possibility of irritation at the site of drug administration.
- It is not use in acute condition, only used in chronic conditions
- High drug level in blood cannot be attained.^{[16][17]}

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 TRANSDERMAL PATCH COMPOSITION

API: Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) is the biologically active component of a drug product (tablet, capsule, cream, injectable, patches) that produces the intended effects.^[18]

The transdermal system is a preferable choice for drugs that experience high first-pass metabolism and the highest degradation in the GI tract, which has a narrow therapeutic window, and drugs having a short half-life (<2 hours) that results in frequent dosing and finally causes non-compliance by the patient.

The following properties should be considered for drugs that are administered through the transdermal route:

- Drug must have a molecular weight less than 500 Da.
- Drug must possess an affinity towards hydrophobic as well as hydrophilic phases.
- Drug should have a low melting point.
- Drugs must have a lower daily dose (preferred less than 20 mg), must be non-irritant and nonallergic and must possess a short half-life.
- Drug solubility of more than 1 mg/mL is preferred between pH 5.0 and 9.0.

Plasticizer: They impart flexibility and enhance the tensile strength of the film." They also influence the drug release, permeability, stability, elasticity (preventing film cracking), and wearing properties of the transdermal system. One of the most important advantages is to control the release rate of the drug, which could be obtained by selecting a particular type of plasticizer and optimizing its concentration in the preparation.

Polymers: Polymer is a backbone of TDDS, which control the release of the drug. Polymer should be chemically non-reactive, should not decompose on storage, should be nontoxic,

cost should not be high. E.g. cellulose derivatives, zein, gelatin, shellac, waxes, gums, Polybutadiene, hydrin rubber, polyisobutylene, silicon rubber, nitrile, acrylonitrile, neoprene, Polyvinyl alcohol, polyvinylchloride, polyethylene, polypropylene, polyacrylate, polyamide, polyurea, polyvinylpyrrolidone, polymethylmethacrylate.

Backing Films: Backing films play a vital role in the transdermal patch and also while using the system. The role of the film is to protect the active layer and safeguard the stability of the system, and to affect skin permeation and tolerance, depending on occlusion or breathability. In order to avoid any type of incompatibility the release liner must be fully inert to the ingredients. It must also be flexible, comfortable and must have good affinity with the adhesive and excellent printability. The most common release liners are polypropylene, polyesters, PVC and nylon.

Release Liners: An anti-adherent coating will be covering the release liners. The role of the release liner is to protect the system when it is in the package, it will be removed just before the application of TDDS to the skin. Release liners play an important role in the stability, safety and affectivity of the patch. Care should be taken to choose the release liners. An incorrect release liner will not permit the easy release of the patch, and can interfere with the active(s) or other components, thereby reducing its shelf life. The most common films used as release liners are paper-based, plastic film-based and composite films. The two major classes of coating are silicones and fluoro-polymers.

Pressure Sensitive Adhesives: For both types of TDDS, pressure-sensitive adhesives (PSAs) play an important role, by serving as the matrix that carries the active like additives and permeation enhancers and the means for making the patch stick to the skin. There are three categories in PSAs: rubber-based, acrylic in the form of acrylic solutions, emulsion polymers or hot melts, and silicon PSAS. For each category there are several sub-categories that give the required flexibility to the patch.^[19]

2.2 Method of Preparation of Transdermal Patches

SOLVENTEVAPORATIONMETHOD

The polymers were accurately weighed and dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol and in the case of Eudragit L100 the chloroform: methanol (1:1) solution was also used and kept aside to form a clear solution. Drug pantoprazole sodium was dissolved in the above solution and mixed until the formation of a clear solution. Then the plasticizer and the permeation enhancers were

added to the formulation step by step and mixed uniformly. The resulted uniform solution was cast on the petri dish, which was lubricated with glycerine and dried at room temperature for 24h. An inverted funnel was placed over the petri dish to prevent fast evaporation of the solvent. After 24 hr, the dried patches were taken out and stored in a desiccator for further studies.

2.3 EVALUATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCHES

- 1. Thickness:** The thickness of the transdermal film is determined by using a portable microscope, a dial gauge, a micrometer or a micrometer at very different points on the film.
- 2. Weight Uniformity:** Weight variation is examined by weighing 10 randomly selected spots separately and calculating the average weight. The individual weight should not deviate significantly from the average weight.
- 3. Drug content Determination:** Precisely weigh the portion of the film (approx. 100 mg) is dissolved in 100 ml of a suitable solvent in which the active substance is soluble and the solution is then stirred continuously for 24 h in a shaking incubator. Then the total solution, after sonication and subsequent filtration, the active ingredient in solution is estimated spectrophotometrically by appropriate dilution.
- 4. Moisture content:** Prepared films are weighed separately and stored in a desiccator containing calcium chloride for 24 hours at room temperature. The films are weighed again after a set interval until they have a constant weight.

$$\% \text{ Moisture Content} = \frac{\text{Initial Weight} - \text{Final Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

- 5. Moisture absorption:** The heavy films are kept in a desiccator at room temperature for 24 hr. They are then removed and exposed to 84% relative humidity using saturated potassium chloride solution in a desiccator until constant weight is reached.

$$\% \text{ Moisture Uptake} = \frac{\text{Final Weight} - \text{Initial Weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

- 6. Flatness:** A transdermal patch should have a smooth surface and not shrink over time currently. This can be proven with a flatness study. To determine flatness, cut one strip from the center and two from each side of the patches. The length of each strip and the change in length are measured to determine the percent constriction. Zero percent necking corresponds to 100% flatness.

$$\% \text{ Constriction} = \frac{I_1 - I_2}{I_1} \times 100$$

Where, I_1 = initial length of each strip, I_2 = final length of each strip.

7. Folding Endurance: Evaluation of folding endurance involves determining the folding capacity of the films subjected to frequent extreme conditions of folding. Folding endurance is determined by repeatedly folding the film at the same place until it breaks. The number of times the films could be folded at the same place without breaking is the folding endurance value.^[20]

3. CONCLUSION

Transdermal drug delivery systems present a promising alternative for the treatment of peptic ulcers, offering controlled drug release, improved patient compliance and the ability to bypass hepatic first-pass metabolism. The formulation of transdermal patches requires careful selection of polymers, plasticizers and permeation enhancers to ensure optimal drug release and skin permeability. Evaluation parameters such as physicochemical properties, *in vitro* release and skin permeation studies are critical for assessing their efficacy and safety. While existing research demonstrates the potential of this approach, further clinical studies are essential to validate their therapeutic effectiveness and commercial viability. Continued advancement in formulation science and a better understanding of skin pharmacokinetics will contribute to the creation of more efficient and patient-compliant transdermal therapies for peptic ulcers.

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4. REFERENCE

1. Kalyanakrishnan R, C Robert, Salinas. A review on Peptic ulcer disease. University of Oklahoma health sci., October 2007; 76: 1005.
2. Yuvaraj G, Manjusha C. A review on peptic ulcer disease. Inst of pharmaceutical sci, Kurukshetra university, Karnataka, 2011; 3: 49-51.
3. Singh K, Kumar R, Pal S A et al., Peptic ulcer: A review. Ins. J. Med. Phar. Drug Re., 2024; 8(2): 39-40. Online Available at: <https://www.aipublications.com/ijmpd/>
4. Chung K T, Vishal kumar G Shelat. Perforated peptic ulcer - an update World J Gastrointest Surg, 2017; 9(1): 1-12. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4240/wjgs.v9.il.1>
5. J Elisabeth, Shell. Pathophysiology of peptic ulcer disease. Physician Assist clin 6, 2021: 604.
6. Julia F, C Alfred. Diagnosis and Treatment of Peptic Ulcer Disease and H.pylori Infection. Fam physicians, Feb. 15, 2015; 91(4): 237-38.
7. K. jaswanth, Kumar Kiran C, P. Venkatesh. Jaswanth et al., UPI j. pharm.med.health sci, 5(1): 2022: 22-23. Available at: www.uniquepubinternational.com.
8. Abdumajidovich J. panjiyev. Risk factors and complication rates for peptic ulcer disease. International scientific journal, 2.
9. Digamber A D, Bathe Ritesh and Patil Manojkumar. An update review on transdermal drug delivery systems. International Journal of Advances in Scientific Res., 2015; 1(6): 244.
10. Wang Y, Zhao XP, Ruan JW, Transdermal drug delivery system of aceclofenac for rheumatoid arthritis and the effect of permeation enhancers: *in vitro* and *in vivo* characterization, Int J Pharmacol, 2015; 11: 456-462.
11. Ghulaxe C, Rameshwar V. An review on transdermal drug delivery system. The pharma innovation journal, 2015; 4(1): 38.

12. Alam Intakhab, Alam Nawazish, Singh Vikramjit. Et al., Type, preparation and evaluation of transdermal patch: A Review. World journal of Pharmaceutical Science, 2207; 2(4).
13. Mohan N, Edwards ET, Cupps TR. Demyelination occurring during anti-tumor necrosis factor alpha therapy for inflammatory arthritides. Arthritis Rheum, 2001; 44: 2862-69.
14. John Lincy. Review on transdermal drug delivery system. International Journal of Pharma Research and Health Sciences, 2014; 2(4): 264-65. Available online at www.pharmahealthsciences.net.
15. Patel Anjali V, and Shah BirenN. Transdermal drug delivery system: A review. Anjali et al. / pharma science monitor, Jan-Mar. 2018; 9(1): 379-80.
16. Joseph RR, Vincent HL. Controlled drug delivery fundamentals and applications 2nd ed. New York: Marcel Dekker, 1987; 523-31.
17. Kanikkannan N, Kandimalla K, Lamba SS, et al., Structure - activity relationship of chemical penetration enhancers in transdermal drug delivery. Current Medicinal Chemistry, 1999; 6(7): 593-608.
18. Biocon.com, Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API); [Internet] Cited Mar 2023 available from, [<https://www.clearias.com/active-pharmaceutical-ingredient-api/>].
19. VaseemRifath Sheikh, D cruz Alison, Shetty Srishti, et al., Transdermal drug delivery systems: A focused review of the physical method of permeation enhancement. Advanced pharmaceutical bulletin, 2024; 14(1): 70. Doi: 10.34172/apb.2024.018 <https://apb.zmed.ac.ir>.
20. Galge. Ashutosh G, Pagire Dipali. A review on transdermal patches. International journal of research publication and reviews, Oct. 2022; 3(10): 1820-21.